

Ownership Structure and Leverage Decisions

Muhammad Ibrahim¹ and Onipe Adabenege Yahaya²

Abstract

This study aims to investigate the impact of ownership structure on leverage decisions in the listed Nigerian firms between 2008 and 2022. This study uses the ratio of total liabilities and total equity as a measure of leverage. The Generalized Method of Moments is used to examine the research hypotheses by focusing on a panel data set drawn from the Nigerian Exchange's 133 listed firms on its Main Board. The empirical findings indicate that ownership concentration, foreign ownership, family ownership and institutional ownership are significant, however, while OC, FO are negatively associated with leverage decisions, whereas family ownership and institutional ownership are positively correlated with leverage decisions. Furthermore, managerial ownership and CEO ownership do not influence leverage decisions. Additionally, firm listing age and firm profitability are significant in influencing firms when it comes to leverage decisions. The study failed to show similar results for firm size and firm growth. Future researchers can validate this paper's findings by considering all the 155 listed firms on the Nigerian Exchange floor as well. Additionally, future researchers may investigate the relationship between these constructs by extending the period of coverage or in other emerging markets. This study's findings may serve policymakers, regulators, investors, lenders, market participants, and academic researchers to get valuable guidance from relevant literature. The Nigerian listed firms may improve leverage decisions by implementing the regulatory framework introduced by the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (2018), also known as Corporate Governance Codes for effective monitoring and protecting the interests of minority shareholders. The controlling shareholders may alleviate principal-agent conflicts by ensuring that foreign, family and institutional shareholders are accommodated. This study contributes to agency theory by considering ownership structure and leverage decisions among Nigerian listed firms.

Keywords: CEO Ownership, Family Ownership, Firm Growth, Firm Listing Age, Firm Profitability, Firm Size, Foreign Ownership, Institutional Ownership, Leverage Decisions, Managerial Ownership, Ownership Concentration, Ownership Structure.

Introduction

This article examines the effect(s) of ownership structure on leverage for the 133 listed firms on the Main Board of the Nigerian Exchange (NGX), over a period of 15 years (2008-2022). Leverage, also known as capital structure, constitutes a serious challenge for companies operating in Nigeria (Awen & Yahaya, 2023; Itopa et al., 2019; Samaila et al., 2023; Yahaya & Andow, 2015; Yahaya & Tijjani, 2021). Several recent studies have focused on the problem of leverage, as indicated in the foregoing sentence, while there has been much research on leverage, few researchers have taken ownership structure into consideration. Several ownership structures may be major determinants of leverage, however, in this article, we would concentrate on the impact of foreign ownership, family ownership, ownership concentration, institutional ownership, managerial ownership, otherwise also known as board ownership, and CEO ownership on leverage. Furthermore, a comprehensive evaluation of leverage in relation to these etiological ownership structures has not been properly and comprehensively examined in Nigeria. This is one of the motivations of writing this article.

Consequently, in this study, we would examine the effect of ownership structure and control variables, such as firm listing age, firm size, firm growth, and firm profitability on leverage, using agency theory. The study covers a period of 15 years (2008-2022). The firms are drawn from the Main Board of the Nigerian Exchange. Leverage, by a way of simple definition is a ratio of a company's loan capital (debt) to the value of its ordinary shares (equity). It is also known as gearing. It is a borrowed capital for (an investment), expecting the profits made to be greater than the interest payable, so that it can truly bear its name, lever, which means to use something for maximum advantage, for example, to maximize the wealth of shareholders. Leverage is good for everyone, because, it is tax deductible, however, too much of leverage is extremely bad, and it could lead to bankruptcy risk or total company collapse. Therefore, there is need to look for change agent stakeholders, in this case, the owners, to come to the rescue of listed firms in Nigeria.

Ownership structure is a well examined change agent stakeholder in empirical literature (Abdulfatah et al., 2023a; Abdulfatah et al., 2023b; Abdulwahab et al., 2023; Abu et al., 2019; Apochi et al., 2022; Awen et al., 2022; Balogun et al., 2023; Tijjani & Yahaya, 2023; Tnushi et al., 2023; Yahaya & Awen, 2022; Yakubu et al., 2023). Furthermore, the nexus between ownership structure and leverage (capital structure) decisions have been empirically examined, specifically outside Nigeria. For example, Pushner (1995) examines the influence of ownership structure on leverage in the case of Japan. The study observes a strong negative relationship between both institutional ownership and leverage.

Also, Brailsford et al. (2002) extend the literature by examining a link between ownership structure and capital structure (leverage), using an agency framework, they argued that the distribution of

equity ownership among corporate managers and external blockholders may have a significant relation with leverage. The empirical results provide support for a positive relation between external blockholders and leverage, and non-linear relation between the level of managerial share ownership and leverage. In addition, de La Brushlerie and Latrous (2012) examine a sample of 112 firms listed on the French stock market over the period 1998–2009. The results support an inverted U-shape relationship between shareholders' ownership and leverage.

This article offers several significance to stakeholders, including policy refining and improvement, performance evaluation and improvement, addition to a body of knowledge in the areas of ownership structure and leverage decisions, and future research problem identification and direction. Also, market participants, lenders (creditors), employees, suppliers, customers, regulators, and tax agencies would benefit from the findings of the study. Furthermore, the present study is significant because it addresses a pressing corporate issue of the impact of ownership structure on leverage decisions of listed companies in Nigeria.

Given the widespread engagement of companies' owners to resolve agency conflicts, understanding the effects of ownership structure on leverage decisions is critical for developing effective prevention and intervention strategies. This study contributes to the existing literature by examining the relationship between ownership structure and corporate leverage decisions. It also shed light on the potential benefits of using corporate owners to resolve agency problems and inform the development of evidence-based corporate governance codes or guidelines for promoting healthy firm financial performance among the 133 listed firms in Nigeria. The limitations of this study include the fact that the data is limited to 15 years and the listed firms are only 133; variables used and the methods of analyses. The next section is devoted to literature review, methodology, results and discussions, and conclusions and recommendations.

Literature Review

Basically, agency theory explores the conflicts of interests between shareholders and managers on one hand and the conflict of interests between lenders and managers on the other hand. Managers tend to use leverage decisions to maximize their own personal interests, instead of the interests of shareholders. Agency theory comes in to play to resolve these tripod interests (shareholders, lenders, and managers) by letting managers know that their main role is to maximize the interest of shareholders and lenders, if any. Based on this theory, the analytical framework for this study is further explained by the agency theory. The agency theory is the most widely used theory to explain corporate governance mechanisms, of which, ownership structure belongs. Agency theory is derived from the concept of principal-agent relationship, which has been defined as the understanding between two or more people for a task to be carried out. Managers have different

motivations from shareholders and lenders (Campbell et al., 2003). Leverage could be used by managers as a gear or lever to maximize their own personal interest. The extent of use of leverage by the company is therefore to enable managers' gain, or maintain their interests. Corporate owners would want to maximize their own interests by way of ensuring the firm is optimizing leverage.

The schematic illustration depicted in Figure 1 shows the framework for this study. It illustrates the interaction with the dependent variable (leverage decisions) and the independent variables (proxied with ownership concentration, foreign ownership, family ownership, institutional ownership, managerial ownership, and CEO ownership). Furthermore, the framework accounts for control variables (which include firm listing age, firm size, firm growth opportunity, and profitability). The analytical framework in Figure 1 leads to further articulation of the model specification in Section 3.

Figure 1. Analytical Framework

Source: The Authors (2023)

Ownership concentration is defined as the shares ownership concentration of all the block shareholders with 5% and above shares ownership (%). Also, foreign ownership is defined as dummy where "1" is assigned when there is 5% and above block foreign institutional shareholders and "0" for otherwise. Furthermore, family ownership is defined as the shares ownership concentration of all single individuals with block shareholding of 5% and above. Institutional

ownership is defined as the shares ownership concentration of all the block institutional shareholders with 5% and above shares ownership (%). Similarly, managerial ownership is defined as directors' direct and indirect shares divided by the numbers of shares (%). Finally, CEO ownership is defined as CEO direct and indirect shares divided by numbers of shares (%). Leverage is defined as total liabilities divided by total asset. Firm listing age is defined as number of years a company is trading in the stock exchange. Firm size is defined as natural log of total asset. Firm growth opportunity is defined as current year revenue minus previous year revenue divided by previous revenue (%). Firm profitability is return on asset, is defined as earnings before interest and taxes divided by total asset (%).

Empirically, Friend and Lang (1988) provide a test of whether capital structure decisions are at least in part motivated by managerial self-interest. It is shown that the debt ratio is negatively related to management's shareholding, reflecting the greater non-diversifiable risk of debt to management than to public investors for maintaining a low debt ratio. Also, Pushner (1995) examines the influence of ownership structure on leverage in the case of Japan. The study observes a strong negative relationship between both institutional ownership and leverage.

Also, Wiwattanakang (1999) presents empirical evidence on the determinants of the capital structure of non-financial firms in 1996. Ownership structure affects financial policy. Single-family owned firms have significantly higher debt level. Only in single-family owned firms does managerial shareholdings have consistently positive influence on firm leverage. Finally large shareholders affect the debt ratio negatively, implying that they may monitor the management.

Brailsford et al. (2002) extend the literature by examining a link between ownership structure and capital structure (leverage), using an agency framework, they argued that the distribution of equity ownership among corporate managers and external blockholders may have a significant relation with leverage. The empirical results provide support for a positive relation between external blockholders and leverage, and non-linear relation between the level of managerial share ownership and leverage.

In addition, Baeur (2004) analyses determinants of capital structure of listed companies in the Czech Republic during the period from 2000 to 2001. According to the results, leverage of a firm is positively correlated with size and it is negatively correlated with profitability. There is the negative relationship between leverage and growth opportunities. Bokpin and Arko (2009) examine the effect of ownership structure on capital structure decisions of firms on the Ghana Stock Exchange. The regression results reveal that managerial shareholding significantly positively influences the choice of long-term debt over equity. Firm level factor such as profitability is a significant determinant of corporate capital structure decisions.

Also, de La Brushlerie and Latrous (2012) examine a sample of 112 firms listed on the French stock market over the period 1998–2009. The results support an inverted U-shape relationship between shareholders' ownership and leverage. Lim (2012) investigates the determinants of capital structure of financial service firms in China, using a relative regression of accounting data for 36 A-share financial listed companies over the years 2005-2009. The results show that profitability and firm size are significant influence factors in financial sector. Moreover, firm size is positively related to the corporate leverage ratio.

Furthermore, Sheikh and Wang (2012) investigate whether corporate governance attributes ownership concentration and managerial ownership affect capital structure choices of Pakistani firms. The results suggest that ownership concentration is positively related to leverage. Managerial ownership is negatively related to the long-term debt ratio. Control variables such as profitability is negatively related to the total debt ratio and the long-term debt ratio, whereas firm size is positively related. Ganguli (2013) empirically investigate how ownership structure impacts the capital structure of the listed mid-cap companies in India. Empirical results on Indian firms suggest that the ownership structure does impact capital structure. Consistent with theoretical prediction empirical results reveal that the leverage is positively related to concentrated shareholding and has a negative relation with diffuseness of shareholding after controlling for profitability, growth and size.

Alipour et al. (2015) investigate the determinants of capital structure of non-financial firms in Iran. The results of the study suggest that variables such as firm's size, profitability, and growth affect capital structure of Iranian corporations. Furthermore, Chadha and Sharma (2015) study the key determinants of capital structure for Indian manufacturing firms. It was empirically found that size, age, growth, profitability, and ownership structure are significantly correlated with the firm financial leverage.

In addition, Hermassi et al. (2015) investigate the relationship between ownership structure and capital structure in Canada, using a sample of 117 firm-years listed on the Toronto Stock Exchange over the period 2008-2011. Their results show that family and institutional have a negative impact on the capital structure. Also, Anh and Phuong (2018) examine whether and to what degree does ownership structure affect the capital structure, using a universal sample of Vietnamese listed firms from 2009 to 2015. The results depict a positive and significant impact of ownership concentration on the overall capital structure of the companies. Further tests indicate that the effect of ownership structure is stronger for short-term debt and bank debt and weaker or even not significant for long-term debt. Institutional investors and foreign investors do not significantly affect the capital structure ratio, they find a non-linear relationship between managerial ownership and the structure of overall debt and bank debt.

Furthermore, Tripathi (2019) examines the relationship between ownership structure and the capital structure of the Automobile Industry in India from 2001 to 2014 by using panel data analysis. The findings of the study after controlling for variables like firm size reveal that ownership structure has a significant and positive relationship with capital structure. In addition, Fayeze et al. (2019) find the most relative ownership structure related factors of influencing capital structure of top 50 non-financial firms listed in Egyptian exchange from 2012 to 2017. The study finds that the relationships between Ownership Structure proxies and Capital Structure are partially supported. Also, the study explaining the effect of Firm Age and Company Size on Capital Structure is partially supported.

In view of these empirical studies, the following hypotheses are stated:

H₀₁: Ownership concentration has no significant impact on leverage.

H₀₂: Foreign ownership has no significant impact on leverage.

H₀₃: Family ownership has no significant impact on leverage.

H₀₄: Institutional ownership has no significant impact on leverage.

H₀₅: Managerial ownership has no significant impact on leverage.

H₀₆: CEO ownership has no significant impact on leverage.

The remaining sections are devoted to methodology, results and discussions and conclusions and recommendations, and references.

Methodology

This section explains the techniques and approach employed in carrying out the empirical study on the nexus between ownership structure and leverage decisions. To this end, the section begins with the research design, closely followed by the population of the study. This is followed by the sample size and sampling techniques, before we have a method of data collections which is closely followed by model specification and technique of data analysis. In this study, the research method adopted was a correlational research design and ex post-facto type of research and content analysis technique. The study is longitudinal covering a period of fifteen (15) years. That is, from 2008 to 2022 employing companies quoted in the Nigerian Exchange.

The population of the study consists of all the one hundred and fifty six (156) listed firms on the floor of the Nigerian Exchange (NGX) as at 31st December, 2022. The financial statements of these quoted firms were statutorily published and made available to the general public. The sampling technique employed was firms on the Main Board of the NGX. The sample size for the study were One Hundred and Thirty-Four (133) firms. This chosen sample size for the study is thus, consistent or in line with the suggestion made by Kerjice and Morgan (1970) that a minimum of five percent (5%) of a defined population is considered as being adequate sample size required for

generalization. In this regard, our sample size is 85.81 percent (133/155).

The study uses secondary data (historical data) collected in respect of the variable captured covering the time frame of fifteen years (2008 to 2022) which were obtained from the financial statements and accounts of the sampled firms. Most previous studies have used annual financial statements. According to Gray et al. (1995), annual financial statements is the main official and legal document produced by companies on a regular basis and an important medium for their communications. Companies exercise control over the annual financial statements to prevent any possible journalistic information distortion or interpretation (Gray et al., 1995). Furthermore, according to Tilt (2001), financial statements are mandatory by legislation to be regularly produced particularly by all quoted corporate entities and by these facts making comparisons quite easy or simple.

Table 1. *Measurement of Variables and Expected Signs*

Serial	Variables and Labels	Notation and Sources	a priori sign
1	Y, LD, Leverage decisions	Measured as total liabilities divided by total asset.	
2	X ₁ , OC, Ownership Concentration	Measured as the shares ownership concentration of all the block shareholders with 5% and above shares ownership (%).	-
3	X ₂ , FO, Foreign Ownership	Measured as dummy where "1" is assigned when there is 5% and above block foreign institutional shareholders and "0" for otherwise.	-
4	X ₃ , FA, Family Ownership	Measured as the shares ownership concentration of all single individuals with block shareholding of 5% and above.	-
5	X ₄ , IO, Institutional Ownership	Measured as the shares ownership concentration of all the block institutional shareholders with 5% and above shares ownership (%).	-
6	X ₅ , MA, Managerial Ownership	Measured as directors' direct and indirect shares divided by the numbers of shares (%).	-
7	X ₆ , CEO, CEO Ownership	Measured as CEO direct and indirect shares divided by numbers of shares (%).	-
8	X ₇ , LAGE, Firm Listing Age	Measured as number of years a company is trading in the stock exchange.	+/-
9	X ₈ , FS, Firm Size	Measured as natural log of total asset.	+/-
10	X ₉ : FG, Firm Growth Opportunity	Measured by the natural logarithms of revenue (Crisóstomo & Freire. 2015).	+/-
11	X ₁₀ : FP, Firm Profitability	Measured by computing from the annual financial statements net profit to total assets (Nurhayati et al.. 2015).	+/-

Source: The Authors (2023)

In this study, the model was specified to capture corporate ownership structure characteristics, leverage decisions, and the control variables used in the study. Thus, the study adapted the model

specified by Akhalumeh and Ogunkuade (2021) which was modified for the purpose of establishing the relationship between dependent variables and the linear combinations of several independent variables captured in the study. The model reflects the identified corporate ownership structure, leverage decisions, and the control variables. The model was specified as:

$$LD_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 OC_{i,t} + \beta_2 FO_{i,t} + \beta_3 FA_{i,t} + \beta_4 IO_{i,t} + \beta_5 MO_{i,t} + \beta_6 CEOO_{i,t} + \beta_7 LAGE_{i,t} + \beta_8 FS_{i,t} + \beta_9 FG_{i,t} + \beta_{10} FP_{i,t} + \epsilon_{i,t}$$

Whereas: LD is leverage decisions, OC is ownership concentration, FO is foreign ownership, FA is family ownership, IO is institutional ownership, MO is managerial (board) ownership, CEOO is CEO ownership, LAGE is firm listing age, FS is firm size, FG is firm growth opportunity, and FP is firm profitability. ϵ is stochastic disturbance, i is firm script, t is time script, β_0 is constant (intercept), and β_{1-10} are beta coefficients.

Thus, our a priori expectations are stated as:

$X_1 > 0$: Means that a rise in ownership concentration generates a decrease in leverage.

$X_2 > 0$: Means that a rise in foreign ownership generates a decrease in leverage.

$X_3 > 0$: Means that a rise in family ownership generates a decrease in leverage.

$X_4 > 0$: Means that a rise in institutional ownership generates a decrease in leverage.

$X_5 > 0$: Means that a rise in managerial (board) ownership generates a decrease in leverage.

$X_6 > 0$: Means that a rise in CEO ownership generates a decrease in leverage.

$X_7 > 0$: Means that a rise in firm listing age generates a decrease/increase in leverage.

$X_8 > 0$: Means that a rise in firm size generates a decrease/increase in leverage.

$X_9 > 0$: Means that a rise in firm growth generates a decrease/increase in leverage.

$X_{10} > 0$: Means that a rise in firm profitability generates a decrease/increase in leverage.

The econometric technique adopted in this study is the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) technique. The rationale for its choice is based on the following justifications: the data have time and cross-sectional attributes that gives room for studying leverage decisions over time (time series) as well as across the sampled firms (cross-section); panel data regression provides better results since it increases sample size and reduces the problem of degree of freedom (Muhammad, 2012); it avoids the problem of multicollinearity and help to capture the individual cross-sectional (or firm-specific) effects that the various pools may exhibit with respect to the dependent variable in the model. Hausman and Taylor (1981) also recommended panel data estimation method because it enables a cross-sectional time series analysis which usually makes provision for a broader set of data points, but also because of its ability to control heterogeneity and endogeneity issues. Hence panel data estimation allows for the control of individual-specific effects usually unobservable which may be correlated with other explanatory variables included in the specification of the relationship between dependent and explanatory variables. Furthermore, the

individual statistical significance test (T-test) and overall statistical significance test (F-test) are used. Importantly, the goodness of fit of the model is ascertained using the coefficient of determination (R^2). Our panel analysis is done after descriptive statistics and correlation analysis.

Results and Discussions

In this section, we start with the descriptive statistics (Table 2), followed closely by the Pearson correlation analysis (Table 3), and finally with the GMM regression results (Table 4).

Table 2. *Descriptive Statistics*

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
LD	1,995	85.409	6.37	72.05	100
OC	1,995	35.098	23.072	0	78
FO	1,995	.405	.493	0	1
FA	1,995	.399	.617	0	9
IO	1,995	32.987	22.35	0	78
MA	1,995	.678	.445	.025	.435
CEO	1,995	.0806	.0628	0	.0983
LAGE	1,995	22.673	15.308	4	47
FS	1,995	8.953	.434	8.15	9.68
FG	1,995	26.506	34.001	-22.5	110.13
FP	1,995	1.512	1.838	-3.83	4.47

Source: STATA 15.1

The descriptive statistics in Table 2 for the variables shows that the number of observations for all the variables is 1,995 (15 years multiplied by 133 listed firms). The mean of leverage decisions (LD) is 85.41 percent, the mean of ownership concentration (OC) is 35.10 percent, the mean of foreign ownership (FO) is 40.5 percent, the mean of family ownership is 39.9 percent, the mean of institutional ownership is 32.99 percent, the mean of managerial ownership (MO) is 67.8 percent, the mean of CEO ownership is 8 percent, the mean of firm listing age (LAGE) is 23 years, the mean of firm size (FS) is 8.953 times, the mean of firm growth (FG) is 26.5 percent, and the mean of firm profitability (FP) is 1.5 percent.

In the same vein, the standard deviation of leverage decisions (LD) is 6.37 percent, the standard deviation of ownership concentration (OC) is 23.072, the standard deviation of foreign ownership (FO) is .493, the standard deviation of family ownership is .617, the standard deviation of institutional ownership is 22.35, the standard deviation of managerial ownership (MO) is .445, the standard deviation of CEO ownership is .0628, the standard deviation of firm listing age (LAGE) is 15 years, the standard deviation of firm size (FS) is .434, the standard deviation of firm growth (FG) is 34 percent, and the standard deviation of firm profitability (FP) is 18.38 percent.

In the same vein, the minimum mean of leverage decisions (LD) is 72.05 percent, the minimum mean of ownership concentration (OC) is 0 percent, the minimum mean of foreign ownership (FO) is 0 percent, the minimum mean of family ownership is 0 percent, the minimum mean of

institutional ownership is 0 percent, the minimum mean of managerial ownership (MO) is 2.5 percent, the minimum mean of CEO ownership is 0 percent, the minimum mean of firm listing age (LAGE) is 4 years, the minimum mean of firm size (FS) is 8.15 times, the minimum mean of firm growth (FG) is -22.5 percent, and the minimum mean of firm profitability (FP) is 4.47 percent.

In the same vein, the maximum mean of leverage decisions (LD) is 100 percent, the maximum mean of ownership concentration (OC) is 78 percent, the maximum mean of foreign ownership (FO) is 1, the maximum mean of family ownership is 9 percent, the maximum mean of institutional ownership is 78 percent, the maximum mean of managerial ownership (MO) is 43.5 percent, the maximum mean of CEO ownership is 9.83 percent, the maximum mean of firm listing age (LAGE) is 47 years, the maximum mean of firm size (FS) is 9.68 times, the maximum mean of firm growth (FG) is 110.13 percent, and the maximum mean of firm profitability (FP) is 4.47 percent. Furthermore, the Pearson correlation coefficient matrix is used to identify the direction and strength of the relationship between the variables. The results from the Pearson correlation analysis are reported in Table 3.

Table 3. *Pearson correlation matrix*

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)
(1) LD	1.000										
(2) OC	0.078 (0.336)	1.000									
(3) FO	-0.135 (0.095)	0.442*	1.000								
(4) FA	0.133 (0.101)	0.171*	-0.102 (0.208)	1.000							
(5) IO	0.055 (0.500)	0.988*	0.462* (0.000)	0.071 (0.381)	1.000						
(6) MA	0.185* (0.022)	0.292* (0.000)	0.244* (0.002)	0.564* (0.000)	0.189* (0.019)	1.000					
(7) CEOO	-0.105 (0.195)	0.104 (0.203)	-0.022 (0.789)	0.152 (0.061)	0.075 (0.357)	0.195* (0.015)	1.000				
(8) LAGE	0.369* (0.000)	-0.160* (0.048)	-0.292* (0.000)	-0.112 (0.168)	-0.172* (0.033)	0.036 (0.656)	-0.243* (0.002)	1.000			
(9) FS	0.016 (0.840)	-0.187* (0.021)	-0.120 (0.140)	-0.035 (0.670)	-0.186* (0.021)	-0.036 (0.657)	0.004 (0.960)	0.283* (0.000)	1.000		
(10) FG	-0.145 (0.087)	0.066 (0.440)	0.037 (0.660)	-0.113 (0.181)	0.081 (0.341)	-0.088 (0.301)	0.183* (0.030)	-0.262* (0.002)	-0.250* (0.003)	1.000	
(11) FP	-0.328* (0.000)	0.076 (0.350)	0.236* (0.003)	-0.076 (0.349)	0.091 (0.266)	-0.013 (0.869)	0.042 (0.604)	-0.183* (0.023)	0.262* (0.001)	0.042 (0.619)	1.000

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Source: STATA 15.1 Outputs

As indicated by the results in Table 3, the bivariate association between ownership concentration and leverage is positive but not significant. Also, the bivariate association between foreign ownership and leverage is negative but not significant at the threshold of 5 percent. Similarly, the bivariate association between family ownership and leverage is positive but not significant. In the same vein, the bivariate association between institutional ownership and leverage is positive but not significant. In contrast, the bivariate association between managerial ownership and leverage is positive and significant. Contrary to this, the bivariate association between CEO ownership concentration and leverage is negative but not significant. On the control variables, firm listing age is positive and significant. Firm size is positive but not significant. Firm growth is negative but not significant at 5 percent. Finally, firm profitability is negative and significant.

Furthermore, the GMM regression results for the model are given Table 4.

Table 4. *GMM Regression Results*

Number of parameters = 11

Number of moments = 11

Initial weight matrix: Unadjusted

Number of obs = 1,995

Prob >Chi² = .0055

R² = .1997

GMM weight matrix: Robust

LD	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P>z	[95% Conf. Interval]
OC	-.1248412	.2632277	-2.47	0.016	-.6407581 .3910756
FO	-.1128243	1.16275	-2.09	0.033	-3.407192 1.150705
FA	.1140145	.1811854	2.36	0.029	-.2411023 .4691314
IO	.1761579	.2669922	2.08	0.041	-.3471372 .699453
MA	.100021	.0545813	1.83	0.067	-.0069563 .2069984
CEOO	-.2581978	.3225721	-0.80	0.423	-.8904275 .374032
LAGE	.1145796	.0402895	2.84	0.004	.0356135 .1935456
FS	-.2507087	1.36709	-0.18	0.854	-2.930156 2.428739
FG	-.0072277	.0168252	-0.43	0.668	-.0402046 .0257492
FP	-.911271	.3415473	-2.67	0.008	-1.580691 -.2418505
/b0	84.6176	12.02232	7.04	0.000	61.0543 108.1809

Source: STATA 15.1 Outputs

The direction of the variables shows that ownership concentration is negative, foreign ownership is negative, family ownership is positive, institutional ownership is positive, managerial ownership is positive, and CEO ownership is negative. On the control variables, firm listing age is positive, firm

size is negative, firm growth is negative, and profitability is negative. In terms of practical significance, the beta coefficients of the variables show that for every unit increase in ownership concentration leverage falls 12.48 percent. This result is in line with our a priori expectation. Furthermore, for every increase in foreign ownership, leverage falls by 11.28 percent. Also, for every unit increase in family ownership, leverage increases by 11.40 percent. When institutional ownership rises by a unit, leverage increases by 17.61 percent. In the same vein, for every unit increase in managerial ownership, leverage rises by 10 percent. In contrast, however, for every unit rise in CEO ownership, leverage falls by 25.82 percent. On the control variables, when firm listing age rises by a year, leverage increases by 11.46 percent. However, when firm size increases by a unit, leverage falls by 27 percent. Firm growth has a marginal impact of .723 percent on leverage while firm profitability has the largest impact of 91.13 percent on leverage. In terms of level of significance, ownership concentration shows significance, foreign ownership shows significance, family ownership shows significance, and institutional ownership shows significance. Furthermore, on the control variables, firm listing age and firm profitability are significant. In contrast, managerial ownership and CEO ownership are not significant. According to the empirical results, as the level of ownership concentration and foreign ownership increase, the level of corporate leverage decreases. In contrast, as managerial ownership and CEO ownership rise, leverage also rises. For these reasons, it is important for managers to develop policies and strategies aimed at improving the level of ownership in their firms. These regression results are mixed, some are consistent with our a priori expectations, and some are not. We expected all the six (6) ownership structure proxies to show negative signs, but only ownership concentration, foreign ownership, and CEO ownership show negative signs, while family ownership, institutional ownership, and managerial ownership are positive. In terms of model fitness, the $\text{Prob}>\text{Chi}^2$ is .0055, which is less than the threshold of 5%, used in this study, suggesting that the model is fit. The R^2 is 19.97 percent, which is large, because it is larger than the threshold of 14 percent. According to Cohen (1988), 1% indicates a small effect, 6% indicates a medium effect, and 14% indicates a large effect.

Conclusions and Recommendations

The agency relationship between managers and shareholders has the potential to influence decision-making in the firm which in turn potentially impacts on leverage. Prior evidence has demonstrated an association between ownership structure and leverage. This paper extends the literature by examining a further link between ownership structure and leverage. Using an agency framework, it is argued that the distribution of ownership among corporate managers and external blockholders may have a significant relation with leverage.

This study examines the effect(s) of ownership structure on leverage decisions of 133 listed firms on the Main Board of the Nigerian Exchange, covering a period of 15 years (2008-2022). Firm owners have been found to be useful to companies in resolving agency problems, including leverage decisions. In particular, ownership concentration, foreign ownership, family ownership, and institutional ownership have been found to be determinants of corporate leverage decisions.

However, the findings show that managerial ownership and CEO ownership have not been well received by corporate shareholders in Nigeria. The descriptive statistics confirm that the number of observations in the panel is 1,995, the mean of the variables is: LD (85.409%), OC (35.098%), FO (40.5%), FA (39.9%), IO (32.98%), MA (67.8%), CEOO (8.06%), LAGE (23 years). FS (8.953 times), FG (26.5%), and FP (15.12%).

The correlation analysis show that managerial ownership, firm listing age, and firm profitability are significant. The GMM regression results show that ownership concentration, foreign ownership, family ownership, and institutional ownership are determinants of leverage decisions in Nigeria. These results are mixed; some are consistent with past studies, while some others are not. Based on the findings of this article, we recommend that stakeholders should take into consideration policies and measures to accommodate ownership concentration, foreign ownership, family ownership, and institutional ownership.

It is instructive to note that this study's findings are limited (1) to the 133 listed firms on the Main Board of the Nigerian Exchange; (2) proxies of ownership structure, such as foreign ownership, family ownership, ownership concentration, institutional ownership, managerial ownership, and CEO ownership. Other ownership structure proxies, such as first largest owners, second largest owners, and government or state ownership are not considered in this article; (3) the period of study covers 15 years (2008-2022). Future studies may consider expansion of the period of coverage; (4) institutional environments in which listed firms operate in Nigeria is weak, and therefore, the findings may not be generalized.

Furthermore, our findings have implications for policy formulation and provide evidence for approach to encourage owners to intervene in firms' leverage. The empirical results provide support for relations between external blockholders and leverage, and non-significant relation between the level of managerial share ownership and CEO ownership and leverage. These results are consistent with active monitoring by blockholders, and the effects of convergence-of-interests and management entrenchment.

References

- Abbas, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Audit committee and financial statement fraud likelihood. *Journal of Contemporary Accounting and Economics*, 19(2), 100365.
- Abdulfatah, L. A., Yahaya, O. A., Agbi, S. E., & Mustapha, L. O. (2022). Mediating effect of firm value on the relationship between dividend payout and growth opportunities of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 14(2), 94-111.
- Abdulfatah, L. A., Yahaya, O. A., Agbi, S. E., & Tauhid, S. (2023). Influence of ownership concentration on integrated reporting of non-financial services firms in Nigeria: Moderating influence of firm value. *African Banking and Finance Review Journal*, 3(3), 35-47.
- Abdulfatah, L. A., Yahaya, O. A., Agbi, S. E., & Tauhid, S. (2023). Effect of firm size on the relationship between managerial ownership and integrated reporting. *Global Journal of Accounting*, 8(2), 43-54.
- Abdullahi, K., Musa, R., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Are CEOs hedge against share price fall? *Accounting and Business Research*, 53(5), 243-263.
- Abdulwahab, A. I., Bala, H., Adamu, A., Yahaya, O. A., & Khatoon, G. (2023). Does board independence moderate the nexus involving ownership formation and financial performance? Evidence from Nigerian Exchange Group. *POLAC International Journal of Economic and Management Science*, 9(2), 1-9.
- Abdulwahab, A. I., Bala, H., Yahaya, O. A., & Abdullahi, M. (2023). Corporate governance committees and sustainability reporting of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (ISSN: 2454-6186)*, 7(7), 1761-1770.
- Abdulwahab, A. I., Bala, H., Yahaya, O. A., & Khatoon, G. (2023). Moderating effect of risk committee presence on the nexus between CEO characteristics and dividend policy: Evidence from listed companies in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Management Sciences*, 24(1), 165-176.
- Abubakar, A. A., Yahaya, O. A., & Joshua, S. G. (2023). Board characteristics and financial performance. *Asian-Pacific Journal of Financial Studies*, 52, 7-19.
- Abubakar, B. A., Yahaya, O. A., & Nma, A. M. (2021). Board features and financial performance of Nigerian banks. *International Journal of Finance & Banking Studies*, 10(1).
- Adewinmisi, G. O., Ahmed, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Audit committee independence and audit quality of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 1(3), 16-26.
- Ahmed, Y., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). New insights on board structure and income smoothing hypothesis. *Asian Economic and Financial Review*, 4(1), 784-803.
- Ajibulu, F. G., Yahaya, O. A., & Agbi, S. E. (2021). Board of directors and quality of financial reports of quoted banks: Evidence from Nigeria. *Umaru Musa Yar'Adua University Journal of Accounting and Finance Research*, 1(1), 79-99.
- Akhalumeh, P., & Ogunkuade, Z. (2021). Ownership structure, financial leverage and dividend policies: Empirical evidence from Nigerian Listed firms. *Journal of Educational Realities*, 11(1), 1-12.
- Alipour, M., Mohammadi, M. F. S., & Derakhshan, H. (2015). Determinants of capital structure: an empirical study of firms in Iran. *International Journal of Law and Management*, 57(1), 53-83.
- Anh, T. T. X., & Phuong, B. N. (2018). Impact of ownership structure on capital structure-empirical evidence from listed firms in Vietnam. *DLSU Business & Economics Review*, 28(1).
- Apochi, J. G., Mohammed, S. G., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Ownership structure, board of directors and financial performance: Evidence in Nigeria. *Global Review of Accounting and Finance*, 13(1), 77-98.
- Apochi, J. G., Mohammed, S. G., Onyabe, J. M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does corporate governance improve financial performance? Empirical evidence from Africa listed consumer retailing companies. *Management Studies*, 12(1), 111-124.
- Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Can the CEO reverse the increasing leverage of listed firms in Nigeria? *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science*, 12(1), 423-433.

- Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Determinants of environmental disclosure quality using Probit estimation among deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Warfare, Command and Capacity Building in Nigeria*. Archers.
- Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Gender and nationality among board members and audit quality in Nigerian Listed Firms. *Audit and Accounting Review*, 3(1), 40-57.
- Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The role of women in sustainability reporting. *Wayamba Journal of Management*, 14(1), 16-34.
- Awen, B. I., Adewinmisi, G. O., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). The influence of ownership structure on dividend policy in reducing agency problems in Nigeria listed non-financial services companies. *International Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 12(3), 99-111.
- Awen, B. I., Lamido, A. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Board size, independence and dividend policy in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 15(5), 72-91.
- Awen, B. I., Onyabe, J. M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Can the board of directors increase firm value? Evidence from the Nigerian Exchange Group. *Korean Accounting Review*, 47(12), 82-97.
- Baba, A. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The powers of audit and risk committees in constraining earnings management. *Accounting Education*, 32(4), 1-17.
- Balogun, J. E., Agbi, S. E., Yahaya, O. A., & Joshua, S. G. (2023). Institutional ownership and firm value of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria: the moderating role of dividend payout. *Nigerian Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 15(1), 85-111.
- Bauer, P. (2004). Determinants of capital structure: empirical evidence from the Czech Republic. *Czech Journal of Economics and Finance*, 54(1-2), 2-21.
- Bokpin, G. A., & Arko, A. C. (2009). Ownership structure, corporate governance and capital structure decisions of firms: Empirical evidence from Ghana. *Studies in Economics and Finance*, 26(4), 246-256.
- Brailsford, T. J., Oliver, B. R., & Pua, S. L. (2002). On the relation between ownership structure and capital structure. *Accounting & Finance*, 42(1), 1-26.
- Chadha, S., & Sharma, A. K. (2015). Determinants of capital structure: an empirical evaluation from India. *Journal of Advances in Management Research*, 12(1), 3-14.
- Cohen, J. (1988). The effect size. *Statistical power analysis for the behavioral sciences*, 77-83.
- de La Bruslerie, H., & Latrous, I. (2012). Ownership structure and debt leverage: Empirical test of a trade-off hypothesis on French firms. *Journal of Multinational Financial Management*, 22(4), 111-130.
- Fayez, M. (2019). The impact of ownership structure on capital structure: An empirical study on the most active firms in the Egyptian stock exchange. *Open Access Library Journal*, 6(09), 1-16.
- Friend, I., & Lang, L. H. (1988). An empirical test of the impact of managerial self-interest on corporate capital structure. *The Journal of Finance*, 43(2), 271-281.
- Ganguli, S. K. (2013). Capital structure—does ownership structure matter? Theory and Indian evidence. *Studies in Economics and Finance*, 30(1), 56-72.
- Hadi, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Auditors' characteristics and accounting information asymmetry. *Asian Journal of Management Studies*, 3(3), 42-56.
- Hermassi, N., Adjaoud, F., & Aloui, C. (2015). The effect of corporate governance and ownership structure on capital structure: Empirical evidence from Canada. *Gestion 2000*, 35(6), 95-114.
- Ibrahim, S. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Which nomination committee attributes matter in improving financial performance? *Journal of Business Management and Economic Research*, 7(9), 231-257.
- Itopa, E., Alexander, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Board of directors and earnings management: Evidence from the Nigerian Exchange Group. *Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 22(3), 45-59.
- Itopa, E., Imam, M., Musa, U., & Yahaya, O. A. (2019). Corporate governance and capital structure: Evidence from Nigeria listed financial services firms. *Journal of Business Management and Economic Research (2602-3385)*, 3(12), 75-89.
- Lamido, I. A., Ibrahim, M. F., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Audit committee and financial performance: Evidence from Nigeria. *Review of Applied Management and Social Sciences*, 6(1),

581-590.

- Lamido, I. A., Yusuf, M. J., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). A meta-analysis of female directors and instability in firm value in Nigeria. *China Journal of Accounting Studies*, 11(7), 325-337.
- Lateef, O. M., Saheed, Z. S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2015). Institutional factors and personal tax compliance in Kaduna State, Nigeria. *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*, 5(24), 146-157.
- Lim, T. C. (2012). Determinants of capital structure empirical evidence from financial services listed firms in China. *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 4(3), 191-203.
- Murtala, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The effects of risk committee characteristics on bank asset quality. *Asian-Pacific Journal of Management and Technology*, 4(1), 35-51.
- Musa, Z., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Corporate governance and firm value. *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute Journal (Humanities and Social Sciences)*, 6(4), 204-220.
- Okodo, B. D., Aliu, M. M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2019). Assessing the reliability of the internal audit functions: The issues. *Journal of Contemporary Research in Business, Economics and Finance*, 1(1), 46-55.
- Onyabe, J. M., Tijjani, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). CEO and integrated reporting: Evidence from Africa listed communication services companies. *Afro-Asian Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 13(2), 86-99.
- Ozoelo, J. I., Yahaya, O. A., & Joshua, S. G. (2023). Audit committee and audit delay of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *Indonesian Accounting Literacy Journal*, 3(4), 226-242.
- Pushner, G. M. (1995). Equity ownership structure, leverage, and productivity: Empirical evidence from Japan. *Pacific-Basin Finance Journal*, 3(2-3), 241-255.
- Samaila, N., Suleiman, R., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Corporate boards and leverage decisions. *Accounting Forum*, 47(2), 307-326
- Sheikh, N., & Wang, Z. (2012). Effects of corporate governance on capital structure: empirical evidence from Pakistan. *Corporate Governance: The international journal of business in society*, 12(5), 629-641.
- Shuaibu, K., Abdulwahab, A. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Corporate governance and dividend policy. *Economics and Business Quarterly*, 6(3), 125-141.
- Sulaiman, L., Abdulwahab, A. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Board of directors and auditor choice. *South Asian Journal of Finance*, 3(1), 38-59.
- Suleiman, U., Popoola, A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Equity financing and financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research in Innovation and Social Science*, 6(12), 618-624.
- Tijjani, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does corporate governance improve energy information disclosure among Nigeria listed manufacturing firms? *Journal of Advanced Research in Business and Management Studies*, 26(3), 15-26.
- Tijjani, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). A bibliometric analysis of corporate ownership demographics and sustainability reporting quality in Nigeria. *International Journal of Managerial and Financial Accounting*, 15(3), 393-410.
- Tijjani, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The impact of CEO female gender diversity and nationality on Internal Control System Disclosure: Empirical Evidence from Nigeria. *Int Research Journal of Management, IT and Social Sciences*, 10(2), 50-61.
- Tnushi, P. T., Yahaya, O. A., & Agbi, S. E. (2023). Ownership structure and dividend policy of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Management Science and Business Administration*, 10(1), 68-82.
- Tripathi, V. (2019). Agency theory, ownership structure and capital structure: an empirical investigation in the Indian automobile industry. *Asia-Pacific Management Accounting Journal*, 14(2), 1-22.
- Umar, M. M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Board of directors and bankruptcy risk using GMM approach. *Applied Finance and Accounting*, 9(1), 242-256.
- Usman, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Board Committees' Independence and Intellectual Capital

- Efficiency in Corporate Nigeria. *The Journal of Business*, 8(1), 36-47.
- Usman, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Do corporate governance mechanisms improve earnings? *China Journal of Accounting Research*, 16, 1-13.
- Usman, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The dynamics between a CEO and risk disclosure in Nigeria. *Accounting and Auditing Review*, 30(1), 1-13.
- Usman, S. O., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Corporate governance and credit ratings in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics, Management and Finance*, 2(1), 62-71.
- Usman, S. O., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Effect of board characteristics on firm value in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Finance*, 47(1), 44-60.
- Usman, S. O., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The CEO power and sustainability reporting of listed firms in Nigeria. *J. of Business Mgt. and Accounting*, 13(7), 106-125.
- Wiwattanakantang, Y. (1999). An empirical study on the determinants of the capital structure of Thai firms. *Pacific-Basin Finance Journal*, 7(3-4), 371-403.
- Yahaya, O. A. & Lamidi, Y. S. (2015). Empirical examination of the financial performance of Islamic bank in Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting Research*, 2(7), 1-13.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2006). Empirical evidence on the effect of size on the profitability of commercial banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Social Studies*, 11(4), 33-39.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2014). Social disclosure and financial performance: Evidence from Nigeria listed firms. *Nigerian Journal of Accounting Research*, 10(2), 47-66.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2017). Firm performance and dividend policy: A panel data analysis of listed consumer-goods companies in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Management Technology and Development*, 8(1), 306-322.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2018). Environmental reporting practices and financial performance of listed environmentally-sensitive firms in Nigeria. *Savanna: A Journal of the Environmental and Social Sciences*, 24(2), 403-412.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2019). Intellectual capital management and financial competitiveness of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. *Enugu State University of Technology Journal of Management Sciences*, 12(1&2), 86-96.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2021). Analysts' forecasts and stock prices: Evidence from Nigeria. *Iranian Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance*, 5(2), 01-10.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Can the CEO improves intellectual capital? *International Journal of Finance, Accounting and Economics Studies*, 3(1), 84-100.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Chief executive officer and firm value: Evidence from Nigeria listed non-financial services companies. *Journal of Economic and Financial Studies*, 10(3), 12-21.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Corporate governance and profitability: An Application of Agency Theory. *Journal of Accounting Research*, 34(2), 406-421.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does Board Gender Diversity influence Dividend Pay-Out? Evidence from Nigeria Non-Financial Services Sector. *International J. of Accounting, Finance and Risk Management*, 7(2), 25-33.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does CEO characteristics affect dividend policy? *Review of Accounting Studies*, 27(2), 375-389.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does CEOs influence earnings management? *South African Journal of Accounting Research*, 36(2), 1-13.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Electronic payments system and economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Management and Economics*, 5(20), 45-54.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Female directors and financial performance. Does audit committee play a role? *Advances in Accounting*, 58(C), 248-258.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Abdulfatah, L. A. (2022). Can auditors reduce earnings management activities? *Review of Accounting and Finance* (ISSN: 1475-7702), 22(4), 429-442.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Alexander, A. A. (2015). Business process management and financial performance: An exploratory study of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Accounting Frontier*, 17(1), 43-75.

- Yahaya, O. A., & Alkasim A. (2021). Sustainability and profitability of listed insurance firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Accounting and Finance*, 6(1), 17-28.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Andow, H. A. (2015). Capital structure and firm's financial performance: Panel evidence of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria. *Kaduna Business Management Review*, 2(1), 1-25.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Apochi, J. (2021). Board of directors and corporate social responsibility reporting of quoted companies in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting, Finance and Auditing Studies*, 7(2), 38-52.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Apochi, J. G. (2022). The board of directors' influence on the intellectual capital of Nigeria listed firms. *Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance*, 37(2), 1-17.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Awen, B. I. (2020). Bank-specific attributes and operational efficiency: Evidence from Efficient-Structure Hypothesis. *Journal of Business and Social Review in Emerging Economies*, 6(3), 1087-1098.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Awen, B. I. (2021). Chief executive officers and bankruptcy of quoted resources companies in Nigeria. *Fountain Journal of Management Sciences*, 10(2), 970-980.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Awen, B. I. (2022). Does ownership structure lead to optimal financial structure? *Seisense Journal of Management*, 5(4), 51-64.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Lamido, I. A. (2022). Corporate social responsibility and financial performance. Evidence from Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting and Finance Review*, 10(1), 107-120.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Mohammed, S. G. (2022). Does board of directors improve profitability? *Accounting*, 8, 269-275.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Ogwiji, J. (2021). Risk committee traits and profitability of Nigerian banking sector. *Accounting, Finance and Management: Texts and Applications*, 01-14.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Onyabe, J. M. (2020). Firm life cycle and financial performance: Evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Finance in Emerging Economies*, 6(3), 723-732.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Onyabe, J. M. (2022). Audit committee and integrated reporting. *European Research Studies Journal*, 25(4), 305-318.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Onyabe, J. M. (2022). Do audit fees and auditor independence affect audit quality? *Asian Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 14(1), 66-80.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Onyabe, J. M. (2022). The nexus between audit committee and audit fees. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 53(6), 966-984.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Tijani, B. (2020). Internal corporate governance and intellectual capital of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 8(9), 98-112.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Tijjani, B. (2021). Size, age and leverage of Nigeria quoted oil and gas corporations. *Advanced International Journal of Banking, Accounting and Finance*, 3(6), 51-60.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Yakubu, I. (2022). Risk committee's influence on enterprise risk management. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 15(4): 120, 1-15.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Yusuf, M. J. (2020). Ethical behavioural disclosure and financial performance of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. *Sustainable Business and Society in Emerging Economies*, 2(2), 13-20.
- Yahaya, O. A., Farouk, B. K. U., Lamidi, S. Y., Yusuf, M. J., & Dania, I. S. (2015). Impact of competition on the financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 6(18), 52-61.
- Yahaya, O. A., Kutigi, U. M., & Ahmed, M. (2014). Country-specific characteristics as determinants of financial performance: Evidence from listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting*, 3(2), 77-101.
- Yahaya, O. A., Kutigi, U. M., & Ahmed, M. (2015). International financial reporting standards and earnings management behavior of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *European Journal of Business Management*, 7(18), 70-82.
- Yahaya, O. A., Kutigi, U. M., Solanke, A. A., Onyabe, J. M. & Usman, S. O. (2015). Current

- assets management and financial performance: Evidence from listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Int Journal of African and Asian Studies*, 13, 45-56.
- Yahaya, O. A., Lamidi, Y. S., Kutigi, U. M., & Ahmed, M. (2015). The correlation between risk management and organizational performance: an empirical investigation using panel data. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 6(16), 136-146.
- Yahaya, O. A., Mohammed, I., & Mohammed, S. G. (2022). Board governance and sustainability disclosure of Nigeria Listed Deposit Money Banks. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 10(5), 126-146.
- Yahaya, O. A., Ohiaka, I. Z., Ahmed, M. N., Mustapha, L. O., Jimoh, O. I., Onyabe, J. M. (2015). Principal components analysis of local government revenue in Nigeria: 1993–2014. *Public Policy and Administration Research*, 5(10), 38-47.
- Yahaya, O. A., Onyabe, J. M., & Usman, S. O. (2015). Determinants of productivity of listed deposit money banks: An empirical estimation using panel data. *Journal of Accounting*, 4(1), 79-93.
- Yahaya, O. A., Onyabe, J. M., & Usman, S. O. (2015). International financial reporting standards and value relevance of accounting information of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Dev.*, 6(12), 85-93.
- Yahaya, O. A., Onyabe, J. M., Yusuf, M. J., & Bilyaminu, T. (2019). Financial mix and financial performance of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Management*, 2(1), 226-237.
- Yahaya, O. A., Tanko, M., & Muhammad, L. M. (2017). Effects of corporate characteristics on earnings quality of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Management Sciences*, 8(1), 47-64.
- Yahaya, O. A., Yusuf, M. J., & Dania, I. S. (2015). International financial reporting standards' adoption and financial statement effects: Evidence from listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Research J. of Finance and Accounting*, 6(12), 107-122.
- Yakubu, I., Ahmed, M. N., Yahaya, O. A., & Agbi, S. E. (2023). Audit committee and audit report lag: moderating role of ownership concentration of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 11(7), 77-100.
- Yakubu, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Auditors' characteristics and variability in integrated reporting gravity. *International Journal of Accounting, Finance and Business*, 8(50), 234-255.
- Yusuf, M. J., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). CEO attributes and financial performance of listed firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Sciences*, 11(2), 112-124.